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ACOUSTIC IMPEDANCE REDUCTION OF MDOF LINERS WITH NUMERICAL AND ANALYTICAL APPROACHES UNDER GRAZING FLOW CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Despite the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, the latest forecasts about air traffic in Europe are predicting a recovery to the 2019 levels by the next two years. Since noise pollution of urban areas close to airports is a serious issue, international regulations are more and more oriented to restrict the maximum allowable aircraft noise. A viable strategy to pursue the low-noise design of the aircraft engines is the installation of acoustic liners on the intake duct and exhaust nozzles. However, the narrow-band absorption of the traditional single degree of freedom (SDOF) liners restricts the noise suppression just around the resonant frequency of the liner resonators. This means that SDOF liners are designed to absorb a well-defined tonal excitation, becoming ineffective when a change in the acoustic frequency occurs. To overcome this limitation, an effective way to broaden the absorption range of acoustic liners is to design a multi degrees of freedom (MDOF) arrangement of the liner cells. This is achieved by adding multiple honeycomb layers of whatever depth in between the rigid back-plate and the perforated face-sheet. Doing so, more than a single resonant frequency is deployed in the audible range leading to multiple absorption peaks in the frequency response of the liner.

In this work, the authors present high fidelity LES simulations aimed at validating an in-house extension to MDOF liners of the semi-analytical model of Hersh. The acoustic impedance of a three degrees of freedom (TDOF) liner cell is calculated from the LES through a three-microphone in-situ method. Then, the numerical results are compared with the outcomes of the semi-analytical model to assess the reliability of the in-house formulation. Both the effects of the

excitation frequency and the grazing flow Mach number on the acoustic impedance of the TDOF resonators are considered for the validation procedure. The close matching between the numerical and the analytical results demonstrates the robustness of the in-house extension of the Hersh model. Moreover, it also suggests that the extended Hersh model is an attractive tool to have quick and accurate predictions of the acoustic performance of whatever MDOF liner geometry.

NOMENCLATURE

c	Speed of sound
C_D	Acoustic discharge coefficient
C_V	Grazing flow discharge coefficient
d	Orifice diameter
H	Inertial length
i	Imaginary unit
k	Acoustic wave number
L	Cavity depth
P	Acoustic pressure
S	Orifice cross-sectional area
S_w	Orifice lateral area
u	Acoustic velocity
V	Grazing flow speed
w	Face-sheet/septum thickness
z	Specific acoustic impedance

Greek:

χ	Specific acoustic reactance
ν	Kinematic viscosity
ω	Forcing pulsation
ω_R	Resonant pulsation

ρ	Density
σ	Porosity
τ_w	Wall shear stress
θ	Specific acoustic resistance

Subscripts:

0	Air values
1, 2, 3	Upper, middle and lower degrees of freedom
<i>ac</i>	acoustic
<i>i</i>	<i>i</i> -th degree of freedom
<i>l</i>	linear
<i>nl</i>	non-linear
<i>ss</i>	steady state

Acronyms:

BPF	Blade Passing Frequency
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DDOF	Double Degree of Freedom
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
DNS	Direct Numerical Simulation
DoF	Degree of Freedom
LBM	Lattice Boltzmann Method
LES	Large Eddy Simulation
LTO	Landing-Takeoff
MDOF	Multi Degree of Freedom
SDOF	Single Degree of Freedom
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
TDOF	Triple Degree of Freedom

Superscripts and oversigns:

*	Complex Conjugate
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INTRODUCTION

The sudden and massive recovery of the air traffic of the present days is putting once again the stress on the noise pollution that strikes people living close to the biggest airports. The need for a quieter civil aviation represents an important challenge for all the aero-engine manufacturers who must comply with the regulations of the Flightpath 2050 document [1]. The aeronautical noise is an issue of primary importance during the LTO cycle, when the flight altitude is low and the aircraft is close to the ground. In these conditions, the noise signature of the modern turbofan engines comes mainly from the fan at approach and from the jet at takeoff. The fan noise is characterized by tonal emissions that are linked to the BPF of the fan and they are radiated frontwards. On the other hand, the jet noise is mainly due to the broadband emissions of the shear layers at the nozzle exhaust. With the aim of attenuating the fan noise, circular rims of acoustic liners can be used to treat the inner surface of the engine intake duct. Acoustic liners are perforated panels that dissipate the acoustic energy into viscous losses thanks to pulsating jets which arise at the perforation pattern and that are driven by the local acoustic pressure gradient. These panels are designed to match the frequency of the tone to be canceled with the resonant frequency of the Helmholtz resonators they are made of. This is obtained by properly choosing the geometry of the Helmholtz resonator in terms of surface porosity, face-sheet thickness, honeycomb depth and orifice diameter. However, the traditional SDOF Helmholtz resonators suffer from a very narrow oper-

ative range, meaning that acoustic attenuation becomes very poor if the resonant working condition is lost.

An attractive solution to widen the absorption range of passive liners is to build MDOF resonators so that multiple absorption conditions within the audible range can be met. MDOF liners are perforated panels in which the number of honeycomb layers sets the number of degrees of freedom of the system. From a structural point of view, these panels are assembled placing a perforated septum in between two adjacent honeycomb layers. Then, a rigid back-plate and a perforated face-sheet enclose the honeycomb structure as for traditional SDOF liners. In case of locally reacting behaviour of the liner resonators (i.e., the excitation wavelength is much larger than the resonator dimension), a lumped parameter approach can be exploited to model the MDOF resonator acoustics. Following a mechanical analogy, the acoustic behaviour of the resonators can be interpreted as the forced response of a MDOF mass-spring-damper system. In the acoustic framework, the external forcing is provided by the tonal excitation, the inertia by the air mass oscillations across the resonator neck, the compliance by the air volume within the cavities and the damping by the viscous effects at the perforated surface. At the same time, the velocities of the pulsating jets at the necks play the role of the displacement of each DoF of the mass-spring-damper system. As for mechanical vibrating systems, also for the acoustic ones a resonant condition is consistent with a magnification of the system oscillations. On the other hand, the anti-resonance phenomenon leads to a total suppression of the oscillations of the DoFs. However, under the acoustic perspective, a resonance is desirable as the larger the pulsating oscillations, the more the viscous dissipation due to the jets. Conversely, an anti-resonant condition should be avoided as an hard-wall-like behaviour of the resonator is retrieved if this occurs. In case of MDOF lumped systems, *N* resonant frequencies and *N*-1 anti-resonant frequencies are expected for a generic liner configuration. Thus, to model the acoustic response of the resonators when an excitation interacts with the liner, the complex acoustic impedance can be introduced. This is directly linked to the absorption coefficient of the liner which is a global quantity that depends also from the area of the lining surface.

The derivation of the liner acoustic impedance is usually based on experimental techniques that aim at determining the reflection coefficient of perforated plates. Under the hypothesis of normal incidence of the excitation, the acoustic impedance of a perforated panel can be derived through the experimental Kundt tube rig [2]. However, this method is not well suited for liner applications where grazing flow and travelling waves are present. For these reasons, the two-microphone in-situ method of Dean [3] is widely used. This technique exploits a face-sheet and a cavity flush-mounted microphone to reconstruct the acoustic velocity at the centre of the orifice on the perforated plate. Then, the acoustic impedance is calculated by taking the ratio between the complex acoustic pressure and velocity at the orifice. The main issue related to the two-microphone in-situ method is that it has been originally developed for SDOF geometries

only. To deal with MDOF resonators, some extensions of the original method have been developed by Zandbergen [4] and Rademaker [5] for DDOF and TDOF arrangements respectively. As it is still quite challenging the instrumentation of MDOF resonators, experimental measurements can be based on non-intrusive acquisitions of the acoustic field through particle image velocimetry and laser doppler velocimetry techniques [6]. However, no information on the local acoustic impedance is provided as these methods are thought for the investigation of the absorption performance of the entire test section.

Another way to evaluate the acoustic impedance of resonators is to rely on analytical models for both the resistance and the reactance terms. Many formulations can be found in the literature starting from the very first theoretical model of Ingard [7] for the design of acoustic resonators. Later on, some corrections to the original model were proposed to consider the non linear effect of the acoustic SPL [8] on resistance, the influence of the porosity and the grazing flow on the inertial length of the air mass oscillations [9] and the interference between adjacent resonators [10]. On the other hand, due to the difficulty of including the grazing flow into a mathematical formulation, some empirical observations helped in building more accurate semi-analytical models for the impedance eduction of acoustic panels. Among all these models, the one of Hersh has been chosen in this work as it is validated against experiments for SDOF [11] and DDOF [12] layouts but no validation is provided for a generic MDOF resonator geometry. Furthermore, the model accounts for the non-linear effects due to the SPL and the grazing flow and an adaption to multi-orifice perforation patterns is also available for SDOF resonators [13]. Finally, the model shows a mathematical structure that can be recursively extended to whatever MDOF configuration as it has been done in the present work.

Finally, a less common way to investigate the acoustic performance of resonators is to use high-fidelity CFD simulations to link the acoustic impedance calculation with a deeper insight on the flow field at the resonator neck. In this context, some recent works aimed at investigating the acoustic performance of resonators under grazing flow conditions by using the DNS [14] or the LBM [15]. One of the main point of strength of the numerical approach is that it also enables the possibility of recreating one of the experimental techniques within the simulation environment. For instance, in this work the acoustic impedance of a TDOF resonator has been determined by enforcing the three-microphone in-situ acquisition proposed by Rademaker [5] on the results of multiple LES simulations. Both the effects of the excitation frequency and the grazing flow Mach number have been considered to build a consistent benchmark data-set. Then, the numerical acoustic impedance has been compared to the analytical outcomes coming from the Hersh model to validate the in-house recursive version developed by the authors.

SEMI-ANALYTICAL MODELLING

As mentioned in the Introduction, the semi-analytical Hersh model has been selected to make comparisons between the analytical and the numerical predictions about the acoustic impedance of resonators. In this section, the theory at the basis of an in-house recursive version of the model for MDOF resonators is presented. Further care is taken to explain the workflow and the hypotheses required to derive the MDOF extension. Starting from the works of Hersh [12] and Bielak et. al [13], the authors have build a model that links together the acoustic impedance of each DoF the MDOF system is made of. Then, the acoustic impedance of the whole MDOF resonator is derived by taking the ratio between the acoustic pressure carried by the excitation and the acoustic-induced velocity at the upper perforated plate. For sake of clarity, in the following a detailed description of the recursive version is illustrated in case of a TDOF squared-cross-section single-orifice resonator. The reader may refer to [12] and [13] for further details about the original model derivation.

Model parameters

Before showing the mathematics behind the model extension, an explanation of the linear and the non-linear working regimes of a Helmholtz resonator is needed. A linear response of the resonator is found when the velocity oscillations across the resonator orifices (i.e., the jets driven by the acoustic pressure gradient) are so low that all the dissipation is provided by the shear stresses at the orifice wall. On the other hand, whenever the oscillating velocity leads to the generation of turbulent structures that detach from the neck ends, the regime is supposed to be non-linear. In this case the damping effect is mainly due to the turbulent kinetic energy production instead of the shear stress dissipation. When a resonator undergoes a non-linear regime, a modification of the resonant pulsation and the inertial length of the oscillations is foreseen.

Coming back to the model theory, the non-linearity can be added to the system due to a multi-orifice perforation, a strong SPL of the acoustic excitation or a high grazing flow speed. For sake of brevity, in the following just the non-linearity due to the high SPL is discussed as analogous considerations can be made for the other sources. In case of SDOF systems, the V_{non} parameter is introduced to quantify the non-linear behaviour of the forced oscillations due to the SPL, according to Equation 1. The presence of non-linearity causes a shifting in the resonant frequency of the system and thus a non-linear correction on the inertial length of the jet oscillations must be provided. These latter are expressed in terms of ratio between the non-linear and the linearized quantities leading to Equations 2 and 3

$$V_{non} = \sqrt{\frac{P_0}{\rho_0(\omega_{Rl}H_l)^2}} \quad (1)$$

$$f_{non} = \frac{\omega_{nl}}{\omega_l} = 1 + 0.04[1 - \exp(-16V_{non}^2)] \quad (2)$$

$$h_{non} = \frac{H_{nl}}{H_l} = [1 + 2.05(f_{non} - 1)]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Equations similar to 1-3 can be introduced to quantify the non-linear effects on the resonant pulsation due to the grazing flow and the perforation pattern alone. The V_{non} parameter tends to zero in case of low SPL, suggesting that in this case a linearized behaviour of the system can be assumed. The linearized variables (i.e., subscript l) in Equation 1 depend just on the resonator geometry and they can be derived through a linearized reactance model as explained by Hersh [11]. More in detail, in case of SDOF systems Ingard [7] suggests Equation 4 to associate the linearized inertial length with the resonator geometry:

$$H_l = w + \frac{0.85d}{1 + 0.625\sqrt{\sigma}} \quad (4)$$

Thus, the linearized resonant pulsation can be found considering that for a SDOF system, the Hersh model [11] for reactance at resonance reduces to:

$$\frac{\omega_l H_l}{\sigma c_0} = \cot(kL) \quad (5)$$

Hence, substituting Equation 4 into Equation 5, a solution for the linearized resonant pulsation ω_l can be obtained. It should be also observed that when the linearization hypothesis holds no more, the modification of the resonant pulsation leads to a variation in the inertial length too. In this case, the non-linear inertial length H_{nl} can be derived through Equation 3. Another option is to use the reactance model of Equation 5 inserting the non-linear resonant pulsation in it.

However, it is not trivial to transpose the same concepts to a MDOF layout, as the three cavities interact one another and questions may arise on how to analytically define the linearized resonant pulsations of each DoF. The cavity depth that appears in the reactance model is now undefined as multiple cavities of whatever size are present in a generic MDOF resonator. For this reason, in this work Equations 1, 2 and 3 have been applied to the TDOF resonator by supposing that it behaves as an equivalent SDOF system. To this end, the linearized resonant pulsation has been derived considering a SDOF resonator with a cavity depth equal to the total size of the TDOF resonator (i.e., three cavity depths and two septa thicknesses). This hypothesis intrinsically means that all the non-linearity present in the system is concentrated on the upper DoF of the TDOF resonator. Although this is

a strong approximation, the analytical results are in a good agreement with the numerical ones as it will be shown later. Moreover, it can be demonstrated that this hypothesis holds when dealing with low excitation frequencies.

Another way to determine the system non-linearity is to introduce an acoustic discharge coefficient C_D of the orifices and looking at its variation while varying the SPL or the frequency of the acoustic excitation. The acoustic discharge coefficient is a measure of the blockage on the orifice wall due to the viscous effects and it can be expressed as a function of both the V_{non} and the excitation frequency. For sake of brevity, just a comment on how these parameters affect the C_D is reported, deferring to [13] for a more comprehensive discussion on this aspect. Linear oscillations of the jets across the orifices are expected when the C_D tends to one. This is consistent with very low values of the parameters V_{non} , meaning that the excitation SPL is small or the system is working far from resonance. As a consequence, an increase in the acoustic resistance is expected when approaching a resonance or when the forcing amplitude is high. Thus, from the TDOF-to-SDOF analogy, a reduction of the actual cross section (i.e., $C_D < 1$ when a non-linear regime occurs) is considered for the upper orifice only. This will result in an underestimation of the acoustic resistance when non-linear oscillations of the jets are set across all the other orifices.

At the same time, a grazing flow discharge coefficient C_V is used to account for the amount of grazing flow deflected into the upper cavity due to the driving forcing. This coefficient tends to zero when the grazing flow speed is low while an even growing effect on the acoustic resistance is expected if the grazing flow Mach number is increased. Furthermore, for medium to high grazing flow Mach numbers, a not negligible impact on the acoustic reactance is foreseen as well. However, this time the assumption of concentrating the grazing flow effect on the upper DoF is definitely reasonable as only the upper cavity of a MDOF system is exposed to the grazing flow.

MDOF Hersh model derivation

With reference to the TDOF sketch in Figure 1, the following unsteady vertical momentum conservation system across the three control volumes can be written in terms of acoustic variables:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_0 H_1 S_1 \frac{du_1}{dt} + \rho_0 S_1 \left[\left(\frac{1 - C_D}{C_D} \right) u_1^2 + 2VC_V u_1 \right] &= \\ &= (P_0 - P_1)S_1 - \tau_{w1}S_{w1}, \\ \rho_0 H_2 S_2 \frac{du_2}{dt} &= (P_1 - P_2)S_2 - \tau_{w2}S_{w2}, \\ \rho_0 H_3 S_3 \frac{du_3}{dt} &= (P_2 - P_3)S_3 - \tau_{w3}S_{w3} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Accordingly to what has been already explained in the previous subsection, from System 6 it can be seen that the

Figure 1: Control volumes of the TDOF resonator

C_D and C_V discharge coefficients enter the convective term of the momentum equation of the upper DoF only. Once built up System 6, to derive the acoustic impedance of the TDOF resonator, a solution for the acoustic velocity at the upper orifice has to be found. To this end, the acoustic pressure P_i at each cavity is expressed by solving a 1-D wave equation along the cavity depth, exploiting the hypothesis of standing wave pattern. This leads to the three following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= -i\rho_0 c_0 \sigma_1 \cot(kL_1) u_1 + i \frac{\rho_0 c_0 \sigma_2}{\sin(kL_1)} u_2, \\ P_2 &= -i\rho_0 c_0 \sigma_2 \cot(kL_2) u_2 + i \frac{\rho_0 c_0 \sigma_3}{\sin(kL_2)} u_3, \\ P_3 &= -i\rho_0 c_0 \sigma_3 \cot(kL_3) u_3 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

From System 7 it can be immediately observed that the acoustic velocities at the lower (u_3) and at the middle (u_2) orifices, influence the pressure at the $(i-1)$ th cavity.

At the same time, the linearized resistance model of Hersh [11] can be used to model the viscous losses due to the steady state and the pulsating shear stresses at each orifice:

$$\Gamma_i = \left(K_{ssi} + K_{aci} \sqrt{\frac{\omega d_i^2}{\nu_0}} \right) \frac{4\nu_0 w_i}{d_i^2} \quad (8)$$

The gamma function in Equation 8 underlines that the viscous losses are proportional to the orifice aspect ratio given by w/d . The K constants are unknown and they must be empirically determined to close the formulation.

By substituting Equations 7 and 8 into System 6, the three momentum equations can be rearranged as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1-C_D}{C_D} \right) u_1^2 + [2VC_V + \Gamma_1 + i(\omega H_1 - c_0 \sigma_1 \cot(kL_1))] u_1 + \\ + i \frac{c_0 \sigma_2}{\sin(kL_1)} u_2 = \frac{P_0}{\rho_0}, \\ \left[\Gamma_2 + i \left(\omega H_2 - c_0 \sigma_2 \cot(kL_2) - \frac{c_0 \sigma_2}{\sin(kL_1)} \right) \right] u_2 + i \frac{c_0 \sigma_3}{\sin(kL_2)} u_3 + \\ + i c_0 \sigma_1 \cot(kL_1) u_1 = 0, \\ \left[\Gamma_3 + i \left(\omega H_3 - c_0 \sigma_3 \cot(kL_3) - \frac{c_0 \sigma_3}{\sin(kL_3)} \right) \right] u_3 + \\ + i c_0 \sigma_2 \cot(kL_2) u_2 = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

At this point, from the third equation of System 9, the u_3 velocity can be expressed as a function of u_2 and it can be substituted into the second equation. The same holds for the second equation, so that u_2 is written as a function of u_1 . Then, moving backwards to the first equation, a second order algebraic equation is retrieved where u_1 is the unknown to be solved for. After some mathematics, the first equation of System 9 becomes:

$$\left(\frac{1-C_D}{C_D} \right) u_1^2 + [2VC_V + z_1] u_1 = \frac{P_0}{\rho_0} \quad (10)$$

By solving Equation 10 for u_1 and taking the ratio between P_0 and u_1 , the acoustic impedance of the TDOF resonator is derived. However, to make it possible, the discharge coefficients must be known and a closure for the acoustic impedance z_1 must be provided. This latter is the acoustic impedance of just the upper DoF as it were decoupled for the remaining ones. It can be demonstrated that the following link between the acoustic impedances z_i holds:

$$\begin{aligned} z_1 &= \Gamma_1 + \frac{c_0^2 \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \cot(kL_1)}{z_2 \sin(kL_1) - i c_0 \sigma_2} + i(\omega H_1 - c_0 \sigma_1 \cot(kL_1)), \\ z_2 &= \Gamma_2 + \frac{c_0^2 \sigma_2 \sigma_3 \cot(kL_2)}{z_3 \sin(kL_2) - i c_0 \sigma_3} + i(\omega H_2 - c_0 \sigma_2 \cot(kL_2)), \\ z_3 &= \Gamma_3 + i(\omega H_3 - c_0 \sigma_3 \cot(kL_3)) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

System 11 highlights the recursive structure that links together the DoFs of the TDOF resonator. More precisely, the generic z_i enters the formulation of the z_{i-1} impedance propagating backwards the link up to the first DoF. This formulation can be easily extended to whatever number of DoFs and a solution for the acoustic velocity u_1 can be found solving a N-equation algebraic system of the same type of System 9. It is important to notice that as a consequence of the SDOF-to-TDOF assumption made at the beginning, only the inertial length H_1 is corrected to account for non-linear oscillations, while H_2 and H_3 are modelled as linear through Equation 4.

HIGH-FIDELITY LES SIMULATION

This section addresses the numerical framework of this paper. Firstly the strategies to create the fluid domain and mesh are discussed, then the numerical setup of the LES simulations is shown. Finally, an ad-hoc subsection is dedicated to the acoustic post-processing of the numerical results to derive the acoustic impedance of the TDOF resonator. In this context, an in-depth description of the numerical implementation of the two-microphone and the three-microphone methods of Dean [3] and Rademaker [5] is provided.

Numerical domain and mesh

As already described in Section 2, the acoustics of a single-orifice TDOF resonator was simulated to validate the in-house model extension. As a first-attempt geometry, three identical cavity depths and two identical septum thicknesses were considered to build the resonator. Moreover, a coaxial pattern of the orifices was assumed to simplify the meshing procedures. Both the domain and the mesh were constructed in the open-source SALOME environment [16]. The numerical domain is composed of the resonator subdomain and an upper bounding box where a planar grazing tone was forced to travel from the inlet to the outlet. The bounding box dimensions were taken to ensure that the lateral periodic boundary conditions did not affect the jet flow across the orifices. A recap of the geometrical parameters of the domain is shown in Table 1.

Orifice diameter (d)	1.20 mm
Facesheet/septum thickness (w)	1.00 mm
Cavity depth (L)	7.83mm
Cavity side (l)	8.62 mm
Porosity (σ)	1.52%
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Bounding box length (L_x)	200 d
Bounding box height (L_y)	40 d
Bounding box width (L_z)	40 d

Table 1: Dimensions of numerical domain

A multi-block strategy was used to fit the domain with hexahedral elements. Although this is not strictly required to run wall-resolved LES simulations, an improvement in the numerical stability has been observed when running on structured meshes. To adapt the mesh to the resonator geometry, the domain was properly partitioned so that quadrangular blocks could be generated. Details of the numerical domain are provided by Figures 2 and 3.

Focusing on the meshing phase, the structured mesh was refined across the orifice regions where the pulsating jets arise. The mesh density in these regions was set to target an accurate discretization of the wall shear stresses at the orifice surface under the resonant condition. Moreover, the mesh should be fine and uniform enough to correctly capture

Figure 2: Numerical domain: Boundaries and dimensions

Figure 3: TDOF Resonator (left) and cavity splitting (right)

the turbulent structures which detach from the neck ends in case of non-linear response of the resonator. For this reason, 45 mesh points were uniformly distributed along the orifice diameter. On the other hand, a coarsening of the elements in the far field was enforced on the upper bounding box to reduce the overall computational cost of the simulations. To do so, starting from the upper orifice outward refinements were specified on the edges of the bounding box aligned with the length direction. However, the outward growth rate of the elements along the stream-wise direction was calibrated to ensure that at least 40 mesh points were kept to discretize the smallest acoustic wavelength excitation. This constraint comes from the need for having a fine sampling of the excitation both in space and time. Then, inward wall-normal and span-wise refinements were selected on the vertical and the lateral edges of the bounding box to sew the mesh patches at the upper orifice region. In this way, a smooth transition in the size of the elements was achieved on the whole bounding box. Furthermore, the wall-normal inward refinement was also required to accurately solve the wall shear stress on the perforated face-sheet due to the grazing flow. The first-cell height was adjusted to target the constraint of $y^+ < 2$ on the perforated face-sheet. This was done

Total number of elements	8.5M
Mesh points per diameter	45
Minimum number of points per wavelength	40
Bounding box first cell height [mm]	0.023
Max. average y^+	0.93
Max. aspect ratio	66
Max. Non-orthogonality	42°

Table 2: Meshing parameters

considering the highest grazing flow Mach number simulated in this work. Thus, once designed to meet the wall requirements under the highest grazing flow Mach number, the same mesh was safely used for all the remaining calculations. Some of the most important meshing parameters are listed in Table 2 while a focus on the mesh refinements on a meridional slice is reported in Figure 4. The reader may note that the clustering strategy used at the upper orifice was repeated also on the following DoFs. More precisely, along the vertical edges of each cavity of the resonator, a tooth-saw distribution of mesh points was used. This latter enabled the mesh coarsening at the middle of the cavity still refining it when approaching the orifices.

Figure 4: Mesh refinements

Numerical setup

The acoustic simulations were run through the open-source OpenFOAM suite [17], exploiting the *rhoPimpleFoam* pressure-based, unsteady and compressible solver. As, the numerical methodology and post-processing have been already validated in a previous work, the outcomes of the simulations will be considered reliable and thus they could be used to validate the Hersh model extension. The acoustic response of the TDOF resonator was firstly investigated in absence of grazing flow, just varying the excitation frequency of a planar and tonal acoustic wave. To generate a large data-set, eleven simulations were conducted keeping constant to 130 dB the excitation SPL. Then, the model accuracy was tested also under grazing flow conditions, keeping constant the excitation frequency to 750 Hz. To this end, four further simulations were run, superimposing the acoustic wave

onto a uniform grazing flow. An overview of the set of simulations is reported in Table 3 where the entries NPER1 and NPER2 label the total number of wave periods simulated and the number of periods considered for the post-processing.

NoFlow	Freq. [Hz]	NPER1	NPER2
Case 1	500	20	5
Case 2	750	30	6
Case 3	1000	30	6
Case 4	1800	36	9
Case 5	2000	40	10
Case 6	2250	45	9
Case 7	2500	50	10
Case 8	3000	60	20
Case 9	3500	70	21
Case 10	5000	100	25
Case 11	6000	120	30

GFlow @750Hz	Mach Number [-]	NPER1	NPER2
Case A	0.075	30	12
Case B	0.150	60	12
Case C	0.225	60	12
Case D	0.300	60	12

Table 3: TDOF simulation matrix

The excitation frequencies that build the no flow simulation matrix were chosen accordingly to the output of the in-house version of the Hersh model. More in detail, the geometrical parameters of the TDOF resonator were taken as an input by the model, returning the acoustic response shown in Figure 5. To validate the red curve, many operative working

Figure 5: Acoustic impedance predicted by the Hersh model for the TDOF resonator

frequencies were selected to cover a sufficiently wide frequency range. The range is truncated at 6000 Hz as from this frequency onward, the locally reacting characteristic of

the resonator is progressively lost. From Figure 5, it can be noted that the model predicts three valleys and two peaks in between them. Recalling that a minimum in the acoustic impedance is linked to a maximization of the absorption coefficients, three resonant frequencies are expected ranging from 250 Hz to 6000 Hz. At the same time, two anti-resonances are likely to occur at around 1800 Hz and 3000 Hz. Thereby, to assess the model robustness, frequencies that were expected to point to different acoustic behaviours of the resonator were simulated through the LES. With respect to the grazing flow simulations, the choice of keeping a constant 750 Hz excitation was dictated by the little effects of the septa on the acoustic response of the resonator at this frequency. As it will be explained later, 750 Hz is very close to the first resonance of the TDOF resonator. Moreover, it can be demonstrated that when the excitation frequency is extremely low, the TDOF resonator behaves as an equivalent SDOF system with the same total depth. It is important to remind that the recursive formulation of the Hersh model under investigation starts from the assumption that the linearized resonant frequency of the TDOF is calculated neglecting the effects of the intermediate septa. As the grazing flow adds further uncertainties on how to correctly take the inertial lengths at each orifice, it is more convenient to test the grazing flow influence under a working condition for which the initial approximation is good enough. Doing so, any mismatch between the numerical and the analytical approaches can be only related to the way the grazing flow is embedded into the model.

Following the OpenFOAM nomenclature, to generate the incoming excitation a pulsating *uniformFixedValue* boundary condition was imposed on pressure at the domain inlet. Then, the acoustic wave was forced to preserve its planar form through a *zeroGradient* Neumann-type constraint on the lateral and top boundaries of the upper bounding box. At the domain outlet, the non-reflective *waveTransmissive* boundary condition was applied to prevent the acoustic wave from bouncing back into the domain. This boundary type is based on the NSCBC formulation of Poinso and Lele [18], enabling an inviscid solution of the Navier-Stokes equation on the boundary for each flow variable it applies to. A traditional *noSlip* boundary condition was used to treat all the solid boundaries while a constant temperature of 300 K was considered throughout the domain.

With regard to the grazing flow cases, the upper bounding box was initialized with a constant uniform speed consistent with the prescribed Mach number. This was achieved through the OpenFOAM *setFields* utility that enables the user-defined initialization of a portion of the whole domain. Thus, the mean velocity is kept unaltered during the calculation thanks to the specified boundary conditions.

The second order centred *GaussLinear* scheme was specified for the spatial discretization of gradient, divergence and laplacian terms of the Navier-Stokes system of equation while a second order implicit *backward* scheme was selected for the time derivatives. The choice of the time-step was driven by both accuracy and stability issues. However, it is well known that the smaller the time-step is, the more

computationally expensive the simulation will be. Hence, the time-step of the simulations was adjusted to ensure that the acoustic waves were adequately sampled in time taking into account also the contribution of the grazing flow speed. To also keep the simulation setup robust enough, a time-step of 1 μ s was set for the no flow calculations. Then, for the grazing flow ones its value was lowered to 400 ns for $M = 0.075$, to 200 ns for $M = 0.150$, while a further reduction down to 100 ns was required to simulate $M = 0.225$ and $M = 0.300$.

Finally the *WALE* sub-grid model [19] was adopted to provide a closure for the LES equations and the simulations were run until the statistical convergence of the monitored quantities was achieved. This latter was checked by looking at the time-history of the acoustic pressure inside each cavity of the resonator. Table 3 shows that at least 18 acoustic wave periods were needed for a successful convergence at any of the simulated frequency. Thus, the simulations were post-processed for a fewer number of periods, discarding the initial transient. This was done to guarantee that the numerical results were not affected by some poor convergence issues.

Acoustic post-processing

In this subsection, some fundamentals and the implementation into the OpenFOAM environment of both the two-microphone [3] and the three-microphone [5] methods are shown. A schematic illustration of the two techniques is reported in Figure 6

Figure 6: Two-microphone (top) and three-microphone (bottom) in-situ methods

In this work the two-microphone in-situ method was used to demonstrate that the SDOF-to-TDOF approximation holds under certain conditions. However, one should not rely on it to validate the extended Hersh model as the method was developed for the acoustic impedance education of SDOF resonator only.

The idea behind the two-microphone in-situ method is to derive the acoustic velocity at the orifice of a SDOF resonator measuring the amplitude and the phase angle of the acoustic pressure at two locations. To do so, once pressure is recorded through appropriate microphones, a DFT is performed to derive the amplitude and the phase angle from the original sinusoidal signal. Hence, the ratio between the acoustic pressure and velocity at the orifice returns the acoustic impedance of the resonator. With reference to Figure 6, the acoustic pressure signals are collected at the face-sheet upstream of the orifice (A_i) and at the cavity back-wall (B). Then, the acoustic velocity at the perforation is deduced from both the acoustic pressure acquisitions supposing a one-dimensional propagation of the wave along the cavity depth. In fact, the face-sheet signal should be acquired exactly at the orifice aperture (A) but this is unfeasible from an experimental point of view. Furthermore, at the orifice aperture the overall pressure signal is the sum of the acoustic contribution of the wave entering the resonator and the hydrodynamic pulsations of the jets. For this reasons, the face-sheet microphone should be placed far enough upstream of the orifice to not spoil the acoustic pressure sampling. Then, the acoustic signal is shifted onto the orifice aperture through Equation 12 knowing the upstream distance l , the grazing flow Mach number M and the acoustic wave number k .

$$\Delta\Phi = \frac{kl}{(1+M)} \quad (12)$$

At this point, knowing the complex pressure at two locations and the phase shifting correction $\Delta\Phi$, Equation 13 is used to derive the specific acoustic impedance of the resonator:

$$z = -j \frac{|p_{Ai}|}{|p_B|} \frac{e^{j\Phi_{AB}}}{\sin(kL)} \quad (13)$$

The phase shifting Φ_{AB} that enter Equation 13 is calculated as the difference between the phase shifting Φ_{A_iB} (i.e., known from the DFT) and the correction term $\Delta\Phi$.

To overcome the restrictions of the two-microphone method, the three-microphone technique of Rademaker [5] can be exploited. This technique can be interpreted as a development of the original two-microphone method of Dean extended to TDOF resonators. With regard to the face-sheet acquisition nothing is changed and the same considerations made for the two-microphone method are still valid. However, the effect of the multi-cavity arrangement on the acoustic-induced velocity at the upper orifice is considered through two more pressure acquisitions performed at points B and C in the upper cavity of the TDOF resonator,

as sketched in Figure 6. From the three complex acquisitions, Equation 14 for the specific acoustic impedance of the TDOF can be obtained:

$$z = \frac{P_1 P_1^* \sin(kL_1)}{P_3 P_1^* i \cos(kx_2) - P_2 P_1^* i \cos(kx_3)} \quad (14)$$

In Equation 14, P_i is the complex acoustic pressure accounting for both amplitude and phase angle while x_2 and x_3 are the positions of the cavity microphones taking the origin of the system of reference on the face-sheet. Thus, in this case x_2 coincides with the face-sheet thickness while x_3 is equal to the upper cavity depth plus the face-sheet thickness.

From the numerical point of view, both the methods were implemented into the simulations through the *probes* function object of the OpenFOAM suite. This latter enables the specification of the spatial location of the microphone through a x-y-z triplet. Then, the field to be sampled is entered to complete the function object definition. In this work, five face-sheet probes were placed upstream of the upper orifice at distances $l_i = 6d, 12d, 18d, 24d, 30d$ as depicted in Figure 6. This was done to assess the sensitivity of the face-sheet sampling to the distance between the microphone and the orifice aperture. Generally speaking, an optimum spacing of the face-sheet microphone should be found. Namely, if the microphone is too close to the orifice aperture, it suffers from the influence of the oscillating jets. On the other hand, also a too far positioning can affect the quality of the results, as a little error on the phase shifting $\Delta\Phi$ (i.e., see Equation 12) is magnified when calculating the acoustic impedance through Equation 14.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this part of the paper, the main results of the LES calculations are discussed. Firstly, the no flow results are shown to provide the validation of the in-house version of the Hersh model under a change of the excitation frequency. The numerical and analytical predictions are compared in terms of acoustic resistance and reactance to show that the model accuracy holds for both the components of the acoustic impedance of the TDOF resonator. In this context, a prior verification of the robustness of the TDOF-to-SDOF replacement hypothesis is provided. This was achieved by comparing the numerical impedance predicted by applying both the three-microphone acquisition and the original two-microphone method of Dean. The way the two-microphone method is stretched to the TDOF resonator is explained in a previous work by the authors [20]. For this reason, only a brief discussion on this aspect will be given in the following. Then, the numerical and analytical predictions of the acoustic impedance under the effects of the grazing flow are compared, focusing on the 750 Hz-constant frequency simulations. Although the maximum Mach number considered in this work is quite low for real acoustic liners applications (i.e., fan inlet Mach number = 0.3-0.4), the good agreement between the LES outcomes and the analytical predictions makes the extended Hersh model an attractive and reliable

tool to quickly evaluate the performance of the TDOF resonator under different working regimes.

Zero-flow condition

The frequency response of the TDOF resonator in absence of a grazing flow is reported in Figure 7.

Figure 7: TDOF frequency response: top = resistance, bottom = reactance

The black dotted curve represents the trend predicted by the extended Hersh model, while the red crosses and the blue dots the numerical values calculated through the original two-microphone method and the advanced three-microphone method respectively. A simple arithmetic average was taken to collapse the set of five face-sheet acquisition into a single cross or dot displayed in Figure 7. Looking at the two graphs in Figure 7, it can be noted that the red crosses and the blue dots are nearly superimposed for excitation frequencies lower than 1 kHz and higher than 3.5 kHz. This is the proof that within these frequency ranges the TDOF resonator acoustically behaves as a SDOF one. However, the equivalent cavity depth to be considered when making this approximation varies with frequency. The key point is that the TDOF can be reduced to a SDOF system if no driving pressure gradient occurs at one or more orifices. In this case, the perforation behaves as a rigid wall and it can be taken as the back-wall where to place the flush-mounted microphone for the two-microphone method. The depth at which the flush-mounted microphone is placed also sets the equivalent cavity depth for the SDOF-to-TDOF analogy. A way to derive the equivalent SDOF depth consists in looking at the oscillations of the jets across each orifice. An example is provided in Figures 8 and 9 where vorticity contours

Figure 8: Span-wise vorticity contours at 750 Hz (left) and 6000 Hz (right)

Figure 9: Oscillations of the three jets at 750 Hz (top) and 6000 Hz (bottom): UH = upper orifice, MH = middle orifice, LH = lower orifice

and a single jet oscillation period across the three orifices are reported for frequencies of 750 Hz and 6000 Hz

As visible from Figures 8 and 9 in-phase velocity oscillations are present at all the three orifices at 750 Hz. This is confirmed from both the vorticity contours and the in-phase time-varying velocities of the jets during an oscillation cycle. Following a mechanical analogy, it can be affirmed that this situation mimics linearly dependent oscillations of the three DoFs and a reduction from three to one degree of freedom is permitted. This is consistent with having approximated the TDOF system with a SDOF one with a cavity depth equal to the total size of the TDOF. Therefore, the flush-mounted microphone can be placed at the last cavity back-wall. Conversely, at 6000 Hz some small jet activity is visible at just the upper orifice. This means that the middle and the lower orifices see no driving pressure gradient and the flush-mounted microphone can be placed

either on the upper and the lower septum. Thus, the two-microphone method can be enforced at 6000 Hz on a reduced SDOF geometry with an equivalent cavity depth of one or two thirds of the original TDOF total size. On the other hand, in the frequency range in between 1 kHz and 3.5 kHz the two-microphone outcome differs quite a lot from the three-microphone one. This is evident for resistance while reactance seems to be less affected by this mismatch. The motivation of the resistance discrepancies lies in the oscillating behaviour of the TDOF system in this frequency range. Here, the conditions of no driving pressure gradient at the orifice aperture or in-phase coupling of the oscillations of the three jets are never met. This is due to the presence of the two anti-resonances of the TDOF system that make the oscillations of the three jets linearly independent. As a result, the SDOF-to-TDOF analogy holds no more and the two-microphone in-situ acquisition fails in predicting either the trend and the correct values for the acoustic resistance.

For this reason, the validation of the Hersh model was achieved through the three-microphone method. Again, from Figure 7 it can be observed that the black dotted curve well agrees with the blue dots on the entire frequency range for any of the acoustic quantities. In fact, a major deviation arises on the resistance part at around 1.8 kHz where the analytical prediction lies well above the numerical one. This is due to the steep slope of the curve coming from anti-resonance condition. In this region of the curve, the acoustic resistance is very sensitive to a change in the excitation frequency so that just a little modification of the acoustic frequency results in large variations of the acoustic resistance. However, this is not an important issue as when an anti-resonant peak is met, the resonator acts as a hard-wall (i.e., zero acoustic absorption) regardless of the value the acoustic resistance takes. At the same time, it can be noted that now an almost perfect match between the numerical and the analytical outcomes is found also in the 1-to-3.5 kHz frequency range.

In conclusion, the zero-flow analyses discussed in this section were aimed not only at validating the numerical model, but also at underlining in which cases the TDOF resonator behaves as an equivalent SDOF one from an acoustical perspective. A more detailed discussion about this last topic was faced by the authors in [20].

Grazing flow condition

This last subsection is focused on the investigation of the grazing flow Mach number on the acoustic performance of the TDOF resonator when both the numerical and analytical approaches are used. As anticipated in Section 3, an upper limit of $M = 0.300$ was set for the grazing flow Mach number due to computational effort reasons. Considering the total number of wave periods simulated and the temporal discretization, 800.000 time-steps were necessary to reach the statistical convergence of the C and D calculations of Table 3. On the other hand, the same total time was covered with 400.000 and time-steps for case B while 100.000 time-steps were enough for case A. All the grazing flow simulations ran on 240 CPU-cores of an in-house cluster taking respectively

50 hours (case A), 200 hours (case B) and 400 hours (cases C and D). To run higher Mach number simulations, a further lowering of the time-step is expected with a subsequent rise in the computational cost that could not be handled with the available resources. Despite this limitation, a prior estimation of the extended model accuracy can be still obtained comparing its output with the LES simulations. Having already demonstrated that the three-microphone method outperforms the two-microphone one for a TDOF resonator, the LES were post-processed using the Rademaker approach [5] only. In Figure 10, the acoustic quantities are plotted against the grazing flow Mach number.

Figure 10: TDOF Mach number response: top = resistance, bottom = reactance

The red curve is referred to the LES while the black one comes from the analytical model. Looking at the resistant component, the increasing trend of the resistance with the grazing speed is captured by both the approaches. This characteristic is definitely reasonable as the grazing flow hampers the feeding of the resonator with the incoming acoustic wave. Therefore, the resistance is expected to grow as it can be interpreted like a measure of the permeability of the resonator branch. However, the resistance growth rate is much higher if predicted by the analytical model. This trend becomes evident starting from $M = 0.075$ onward and an intersection between the red and the black curves occurs at around $M = 0.0875$. A possible explanation to these trends lies in the way the grazing flow discharge coefficient C_V is calculated in the model. It should be reminded that in the model formulation the C_V is not a function of the C_D meaning that the non-linear effects due to the SPL and the grazing flow are uncorrelated. At the same time the lineariza-

Figure 11: Spanwise vorticity contours: $M = 0.075$ (top left), $M = 0.150$ (top right), $M = 0.300$ (bottom)

tion hypothesis made for the middle and the lower cavities might have affected the recursive link between the acoustic impedances of the DoFs. As shown by the vorticity contours in Figure 11, the grazing flow speed does not strongly affect the oscillation pattern across the orifices which is very similar to the one of Figure 8. As a contraction of the jet flow is well marked also for the second and the third DoFs, it can be easily deduced that the linearization hypothesis is not well suited when the excitation frequency is 750 Hz. Although it cannot be excluded that some errors have arisen from the numerical post-processing, the resistance trend predicted by the LES is more coherent than the analytical one. Looking again to Figure 11, it can be observed that some vorticity is still produced at the upper cavity for $M = 0.300$ even though the amount of acoustic energy that enters the resonator branch is reduced. This evidence cannot be linked to a resistance value of around 5.0 (i.e., hard-wall-like behavior) as the analytical models would suggest. Moreover, from the reactance trend of Figure 10, it is clear that the grazing flow does not strongly alter the resonant frequency of the TDOF resonator. The acoustic reactance decreases from -0.2 at the no-flow condition to -0.7 at $M = 0.300$ meaning that for an excitation frequency of 750 Hz the system is still working close to resonance. Remembering that close to resonance the acoustic impedance tends to the resistance part, an impedance magnitude of 5.0 would be quite unrealistic.

With regard to the reactance trend, a very close match between the analytical and the numerical results is found. Both the approaches catch the reactance decrease with the grazing flow that causes a slight shifting of the resonant frequency to higher values. Moreover, a flattening of the trend is visible when increasing the Mach number on both the curves, meaning that no further influence of the grazing flow is expected from a certain threshold onward. The flattening trend

is more pronounced on the numerical curve implying that the saturating behaviour is anticipated. This can be related to the way the inertial lengths are modeled as their formulation enters the reactance model. It can be reasonably assumed that a non-linear modelling at all the DoFs could improve the matching between the numerical and the analytical reactance, especially at the lower grazing speeds.

Finally, from these analyses it can be concluded that the good agreement between the extended Hersh model and the LES under grazing flow conditions is restricted to the reactance component. With respect to the resistance component, further investigations are needed to understand how to modify the implementation of the C_V which has been found to be the parameter affecting the resistance the most. From these considerations, it is clear that the matching between the analytical and numerical acoustic responses is not as impressive as the one in absence of grazing flow. Clearly, the no flow condition is much simpler to be simulated than the grazing one. Thus, the mismatch encountered when activating the grazing flow might be also related to numerical issues like errors propagated during the post-processing, a not fully convergent simulation or an inappropriate computational mesh. It is recalled that due to computational cost issues, the same numerical mesh was used for all the simulations. Hence, the poorer resolution of the simulations at the higher grazing flow Mach numbers might have affected the overall quality of the results. In light of these considerations, the authors are planning to test the margin of improvement of the LES results running the same cases on finer meshes and using higher-order numerical schemes.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper a validation of a recursive version of the Hersh model for MDOF resonators has been provided through a high-fidelity LES methodology. Starting from the Hersh model for SDOF resonators, the authors have developed an in-house formulation to extend the original theory to whatever MDOF geometry. The reliability of the analytical predictions about the acoustic quantities (i.e., resistance and reactance) has been assessed through different LES simulation on a simplified single-orifice TDOF layout. The acoustic response of the resonator has been derived with both the analytical and the numerical approaches, investigating the effects of the acoustic forcing and the grazing flow Mach number separately. Then, comparisons between the outcomes have been made to judge the quality of the analytical TDOF formulation. A very close match between the model and the simulations has been found in the case of zero grazing flow. Moreover, it has been also demonstrated in which cases the acoustics of a MDOF resonator can be reduced to the one of an equivalent SDOF system. To this end, the acoustic impedance of the TDOF resonator has been calculated by applying the two-microphone and the three-microphone experimental techniques within the numerical framework. From this analysis, it has been shown that for frequencies lower than 1 kHz or higher than 3.5 kHz, the resonator under investigation can be substituted with an equivalent SDOF system taking a cavity depth equal to one, two or

three thirds of the original total size. The very good agreement between the numerical and the analytical results suggests that in absence of grazing flow, the model outcomes are well reliable to design a MDOF resonator without the need for running time-consuming numerical simulations.

On the other hand, some discrepancies have come out when investigating the influence of the Mach number, especially on the resistance trend. In these cases, the model reliability is not always warranted and the LES approach should be preferred when designing acoustic liners. Nonetheless, the mismatch between the model and the simulation outcomes can be motivated by both the approximations that lie behind the recursive formulation of the model and by numerical issues. Concerning the first aspect, a more suitable implementation of the grazing flow discharge coefficient may help in better representing the physics of the jet oscillations. To this end, also a coupling between the SPL and the grazing flow effects should be introduced. At the same time, also a mesh sensitivity analysis may be useful to understand how much the accuracy of the LES simulations suffers from the numerical discretization of the domain. This may be an issue especially close to the face-sheet and the orifice walls where a too coarse mesh may result in an underestimation of the viscous shear. In addition, it should be checked if the discrepancies do not come from errors in the post-processing. For instance, when applying the in-situ methods, the impedance eduction can be highly affected by small errors in deriving the phase angle of the pressure signal. Hence, it could worth taking an average impedance using a larger set of face-sheet probes to compensate any error.

Finally, a further verification of the model reliability may be provided by experimental measurements on the TDOF resonator geometry investigated in this work.

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